

Conceptual-DFT insights on the structure and reactivity of di-*n*-butyltin(IV) derivative of chlordiazepoxide

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Abstract : The role of conceptual-DFT in understanding the structure and reactivity of *n*-Bu₂SnL₂, where L is the monoanion of chlordiazepoxide (LH), a benzodiazepine derivative with hypnotic action, have been highlighted using the Gaussian09 software package. The molecular geometries of LH and *n*-Bu₂SnL₂ were optimized at B3LYP/6-31G(d,p) and B3LYP/6-31G(d,p)/Def2-SVP(Sn) level of theory, respectively. Harmonic vibrational frequencies were computed at the same level of theory to find true potential energy surface minima. The atomic charges at all the atoms were calculated using Mulliken Population Analysis, Hirshfeld Population Analysis and Natural Population Analysis. The charge distribution within the studied complex is explained on the basis of conceptual-DFT based local reactivity descriptors using the finite difference approximation method. The study signifies an electron deficient Sn centre which further supports the biological efficacy of organotin(IV) complexes. Among the atoms coordinated to the central Sn atom, oxygen from one LH unit is nucleophilic, whereas the second oxygen atom from the other LH unit is electrophilic in nature. The results provide an insight into the efficacy of computational methods in understanding the structure and reactivity of organotin(IV) derivatives of drug molecules.

Keywords : Chlordiazepoxide, conceptual-DFT, di-*n*-butyltin(IV), organotin(IV), reactivity descriptors.

Introduction

The contemporary research has drawn considerable research interest in organotin(IV) compounds due to their structural diversity, apart from their wide range of industrial and biological applications¹. These compounds which are characterized by the presence of tetravalent Sn centres and at least one covalent Sn-C bond, often form structures in which previously tetravalent Sn atoms become hypervalent², owing to the involvement of Sn atoms in additional inter- and/or intra-molecular interactions due to the pronounced electron-acceptor ability of the Sn atoms. These interactions get strengthened and lead to the formation of coordination (dative) bonds in the presence of electron donors which can provide a lone electron pair to the Sn atom. Apart from such unique structural features, in recent decades organotin(IV) compounds have found possible use as potential biologically active non-platinum chemotherapeutic metallopharmaceuticals having anti-tumour activity³⁻⁷.

Further, in the last two decades the complexation of organotin(IV) with active drugs as ligands having hetero donor atoms (N/O/S) such as, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs)⁸⁻¹³, antibiotics¹⁴, quinolone antibacterials^{14,15}, anti-hypertensive drugs¹⁶, and antivirals¹⁷, has emerged as an approach to prepare new compounds with better or different pharmacological profile than that of the free ligand. A few among these studied organotin(IV) complexes have been reported to exhibit good *in vitro* anticancer^{13,14,17}, antituberculosis^{9,12} and antiviral activities^{14,17}. Recently¹⁸, a series of organotin(IV) complexes of chlordiazepoxide (LH, Fig. 1(a)), a benzodiazepine derivative with amnestic, anticonvulsant, anxiolytic, hypnotic and skeletal muscle relaxant properties¹⁹, have been synthesized, spectroscopically characterized, and their potential biological application has been analysed by screening against several antibacterial indicator strains. For instance, di-*n*-butyltin(IV) complex of LH exhibited good inhibition against *Escherichia coli* and *Vibrio cholera*¹⁸.

Fig. 1. Structure (along with atom number) of (a) chlordiazepoxide (LH) and (b) di-*n*-butyltin(IV) derivative of chlordiazepoxide.

A better understanding on the structure and activity of organotin-drug system can be obtained with an aid of its detailed electronic structure obtained within the preview of DFT based quantum-chemical methods. Though, the geometric structures of several organotin(IV) derivatives with ligands containing hetero donor atoms such as N/O/S are credibly represented by quantum-chemical calculations performed within a domain of DFT^{20–24}, the structure-reactivity analysis based on conceptual-DFT based local reactivity descriptors is not reported yet. The study of these descriptors to comprehend the electronic structure of organotin(IV) complexes which has far reaching consequences on its interaction with macromolecular receptors is indispensable for the design of new metallo-pharmaceuticals. Thus, in order to gain a better insight into the physicochemical and biological properties of organotin(IV) complexes with drugs a thorough knowledge of their electronic and geometric molecular structures is significant. As a part of our systematic work on structure and reactivity study of organotin(IV)-drug system in the light of conceptual-DFT based quantum-chemical calculations^{25,26}, the present work highlights the role of conceptual-DFT based local reactivity descriptors in understanding the structure and reactivity of di-*n*-butyltin(IV) derivative of chlordiazepoxide (*n*-Bu₂SnL₂, where L is the monoanion of chlordiazepoxide) (Fig. 1(b)). The conceptual-DFT based local reactivity descriptors thus calculated are interpreted in terms of electronic distribution within the complex to account for its binding towards macromolecular receptors.

Theoretical background

In the preview of conceptual-DFT, local reactivity descriptors have been proposed which have potential use in predicting local (site) reactivity (selectivity) of a chemical species. These local properties may vary from point to point in space and are one-point (\vec{r}) functions, and hence they are the key to determine the most reactive points in the molecule^{27,28}. The local reactivity descriptors discussed in the present study are :

Fukui function ($f(\vec{r})$) : For a system undergoing a change from one ground state to another, the change in electronic chemical potential (μ) associated with a change in the number of electrons, N , and/or an external potential $v(\vec{r})$ is^{28,29} :

$$d\mu = \left(\frac{\partial \mu}{\partial N} \right)_{v(\vec{r})} dN + \int \left(\frac{\delta \mu}{\delta v(\vec{r})} \right)_N \delta v(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} \quad (1)$$

$$d\mu = \eta dN + N + \int \left(\frac{\delta \mu}{\delta v(\vec{r})} \right)_N \delta v(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} \quad (2)$$

Taking the derivative of μ with respect to $v(\vec{r})$ and applying the Maxwell relation, an orbital-controlled descriptor named as Fukui function ($f(\vec{r})$) is obtained, which is the space-dependent (local) derivative of electronic chemical potential, defined as^{27,28,30} :

$$f(\vec{r}) = \left(\frac{\delta \mu}{\delta v(\vec{r})} \right)_N = \left(\frac{\partial \rho(\vec{r})}{\partial N} \right)_{v(\vec{r})} \quad (3)$$

The Fukui function can be interpreted either as the change of the electron density $\rho(\vec{r})$ at each point \vec{r} when the total number of electrons is changed or as the sensitivity of a system's electronic chemical potential to an external perturbation at a particular point \vec{r} ²⁷. When the molecule is accepting electrons, we have $f^+(\vec{r})$, the index for a nucleophilic attack provoking an electron increase in the system :

$$f^+(\vec{r}) = \left(\frac{\partial \rho(\vec{r})}{\partial N} \right)_{v(\vec{r})}^+ \quad (4)$$

When the molecule is donating electrons, we have $f^-(\vec{r})$, the index for an electrophilic attack provoking an electron decrease in the system :

$$f^-(\vec{r}) = \left(\frac{\partial \rho(\vec{r})}{\partial N} \right)_{v(\vec{r})}^- \quad (5)$$

In a frozen core orbital approximation approach, the $f^+(\vec{r})$ reduces to $\rho(\vec{r})^{\text{LUMO}}$ and $f^-(\vec{r})$ reduces to $\rho(\vec{r})^{\text{HOMO}}$ ^{27,29-31}. Further, the Fukui functions can be represented mathematically in terms of frontier molecular orbitals, as^{27,29-32} :

$$f^+(\vec{r}) = \left| \phi_{(\vec{r})}^{N+1} \right|^2 + \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{\partial \left| \phi_{(\vec{r})}^{(i)} \right|^2}{\partial N} \right)_{v(\vec{r})}$$

$$\approx \left| \phi_{(\vec{r})}^{\text{LUMO}} \right|^2 = \rho_{(\vec{r})}^{\text{LUMO}} \quad (6)$$

$$f^-(\vec{r}) = \left| \phi_{(\vec{r})}^{N+1} \right|^2 + \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{\partial \left| \phi_{(\vec{r})}^{(i)} \right|^2}{\partial N} \right)_{v(\vec{r})}$$

$$\approx \left| \phi_{(\vec{r})}^{\text{HOMO}} \right|^2 = \rho_{(\vec{r})}^{\text{HOMO}} \quad (7)$$

Moreover, the integration of the Fukui function along the portion of space that could be attributed to a certain atom belonging to a molecule leads to condensed-to-atoms Fukui functions (i.e. Fukui indices)²⁷⁻³². This in combination with the finite-difference approximation yields for the atom site k , Fukui indices (f^+ and f^-) which can be described in terms of the atomic populations (p), as^{27,28,30} :

$$f^+(k) = \int \left(\frac{\partial \rho_{(\vec{r})}^k}{\partial N} \right)_{v(\vec{r})}^+ d(\vec{r})$$

$$= \left(\frac{\partial p^k}{\partial N} \right)_{v(\vec{r})}^+ \cong p_{N+1}(k) - p_N(k) \quad (8)$$

$$f^-(k) = \int \left(\frac{\partial \rho_{(\vec{r})}^k}{\partial N} \right)_{v(\vec{r})}^- d(\vec{r})$$

$$= \left(\frac{\partial p^k}{\partial N} \right)_{v(\vec{r})}^- \cong p_N(k) - p_{N-1}(k) \quad (9)$$

where, $p(k)$ denotes the electronic population of atom k of the reference system (molecule).

Local softness ($s(\vec{r})$) : The local softness ($s(\vec{r})$) is a local reactivity descriptor which describes the response of any particular site of a chemical species (in terms of the change in electron density $\rho(\vec{r})$ to any global change in its electronic chemical potential values. The local softness can be expressed as^{27,28} :

$$s(\vec{r}) = \left(\frac{\partial \rho(\vec{r})}{\partial \mu} \right)_{v(\vec{r})} = \left(\frac{\partial \rho(\vec{r})}{\partial N} \right)_{v(\vec{r})} \left(\frac{\partial N}{\partial \mu} \right)_{v(\vec{r})}$$

$$= f(\vec{r}) S \quad (10)$$

where, $S = \left(\frac{\partial N}{\partial \mu} \right)_{v(\vec{r})}$ is the total softness. This in combination with the finite-difference approximation yields for the atom site k , different local softnesses (s^+ and s^-) which can be described in terms of the atomic populations (p), as^{27,28,33} :

$$s^+(k) \cong [p_{N+1}(k) - p_N(k)] S$$

(for a nucleophilic attack on the system) (11)

$$s^-(k) \cong [p_N(k) - p_{N-1}(k)] S$$

(for an electrophilic attack on the system) (12)

where, $p(k)$ denotes the electronic population of atom k of the reference system (molecule) and S is the global softness.

Relative nucleophilicity and relative electrophilicity : The individual values of $s^+(k)$ and $s^-(k)$ are strongly influenced by the basis set or the correlation effects. Further, in some systems, the centres with high electrophilicity (i.e. having high $s^+(k)$ values) also show high nucleophilicity (i.e. having high $s^-(k)$ values), which indirectly suggests that for a reliable trend of reactivity both these need to be considered. Hence, two indexes the relative nucleophilicity and a relative electrophilicity are defined in the atomic scale, as^{27,34} :

$$\left(\frac{s^-(k)}{s^+(k)} \right) \text{ (relative nucleophilicity)} \quad (13)$$

$$\left(\frac{s^+(k)}{s^-(k)} \right) \text{ (relative electrophilicity)} \quad (14)$$

Local electrophilicity index ($\omega(\vec{r})$) : Local electrophi-

licity index ($\omega(\vec{r})$) contains the information of global reactivity descriptors as well as the site selectivity of a molecule toward electrophilic and nucleophilic attack³⁵. The different forms of $\omega(\vec{r})$ are defined as^{28,36}:

$$\omega^\alpha(\vec{r}) = \omega^{f^\alpha}(\vec{r}) \quad (15)$$

where, $\alpha = +$ and $-$, respectively, for a nucleophilic and an electrophilic attack on the system. The corresponding condensed-to-atom forms of the philicity index for atom k , can be described in terms of the atomic populations (p), as²⁸:

$$\omega^+(k) \equiv [p_{N+1}(k) - p_N(k)]\omega$$

(for a nucleophilic attack on the system) (16)

$$\omega^-(k) \equiv [p_N(k) - p_{N-1}(k)]\omega$$

(for an electrophilic attack on the system) (17)

where, $p(k)$ denotes the electronic population of atom k of the reference system (molecule) and ω is the electrophilicity index

$$\left(= -\Delta E \equiv \frac{\mu^2}{2\eta} \right).$$

Local hardness ($\eta(\vec{r})$): The local hardness ($\eta(\vec{r})$) is defined as^{27,37}:

$$\eta(\vec{r}) = \left(\frac{\delta\mu}{\delta\rho(\vec{r})} \right)_{\nu(\vec{r})} \quad (18)$$

However, $\eta(\vec{r})$ is dependent on N , and in order to have its broader applicability as a reliable intermolecular reactivity descriptor the removal of its dependence on N is necessary. This result in defining the hardness potential, a combination of a global property (the total number of electrons, N) and a local reactivity descriptor (the local hardness, $\eta(\vec{r})$), for the system as^{27,38}:

$$h(\vec{r}) = N\eta(\vec{r}) \quad (19)$$

The hardness potential $h(\vec{r})$ can be expressed as:

$$h(\vec{r}) = -V_{el}(\vec{r}) \quad (20)$$

where, $V_{el}(\vec{r})$ is the electronic part of the molecular electrostatic potential as:

$$V_{el}(\vec{r}) = -\int \frac{\rho(\vec{r}')}{|\vec{r}-\vec{r}'|} d\tau' \quad (27,39)$$

The two variants of hardness potential $h(\vec{r})$, $\Delta^+h(\vec{r})$ and $\Delta^-h(\vec{r})$, measures reactivity towards an approaching nucleophilic and electrophilic reagent, respectively^{37,40}. The values of these variants of hardness po-

tential, when evaluated at the nucleus (i.e., $\Delta^+h(\vec{r})|_{r \rightarrow 0}$ and $\Delta^-h(\vec{r})|_{r \rightarrow 0}$) of a particular atom k can be calculated as $\Delta^+h(k)$ and $\Delta^-h(k)$, respectively as³⁷:

For the nucleophilic attack on the system,

$$\Delta^+h(k) = h^{N+1}(k) - h^N(k) = -[V_{el}^{N+1}(k) - V_{el}^N(k)] \quad (21)$$

For an electrophilic attack on the system,

$$\Delta^-h(k) = h^N(k) - h^{N-1}(k) = -[V_{el}^N(k) - V_{el}^{N-1}(k)] \quad (22)$$

where, $V_{el}^N(k)$, $V_{el}^{N+1}(k)$ and $V_{el}^{N-1}(k)$ represents the electronic part of the molecular electrostatic potential for N , $N+1$ and $N-1$ electron system, respectively.

Dual reactivity descriptor: Dual reactivity descriptor is a selectivity index which is defined as⁴¹:

$$f^2(k) = [f^+(k) - f^-(k)] \quad (23)$$

If $f^2(k) > 0$, a particular site (or atom) in the molecule is favoured for a nucleophilic attack, whereas if $f^2(k) < 0$, the site is susceptible for an electrophilic attack.

Results and discussion

The conceptual-DFT based local reactivity descriptors described above, which are considered to predict the regioselectivity of the atoms in LH and $n\text{-Bu}_2\text{SnL}_2$, have been calculated at all the atoms with three different population analysis schemes viz. MPA, HPA and NPA. The results based on NPA scheme at the selected atoms of LH and $n\text{-Bu}_2\text{SnL}_2$ are presented in Table 1, and those based on MPA and HPA schemes are presented in Tables 2 and 3, respectively. The variation of Fukui function index and local softness; and local electrophilicity and hardness potential at the selected atoms of $n\text{-Bu}_2\text{SnL}_2$ based on NPA scheme is presented in Figs. 2 and 3, respectively.

Since, there are some differences between the atomic charges obtained from MPA, HPA and NPA scheme, hence Fukui indices will be highly dependent on the population analysis method. The Fukui function $f^+(\vec{r})$ measures the reactivity towards the nucleophilic attack on the system, hence its large value at a particular site indicates that the site is capable of accepting electron density, similarly, the Fukui function $f^-(\vec{r})$ measures the reactivity towards an electrophilic attack on the system, hence its large value at a particular site indicates that the site is an electron donating site³⁰. Further, Parr and Yang had proposed that larger value of Fukui function indicates more reactivity²⁹, and hence, for a particular atomic centre in the molecule,

Table 1. Conceptual-DFT based local reactivity descriptors at the selected atoms in chlordiazepoxide (LH) and *n*-Bu₂SnL₂, based on NPA scheme calculated at B3LYP/6-31G(d,p) and B3LYP/6-31G(d,p)/Def2-SVP(Sn) level of theory, respectively^a

System	Atom	Fukui function ^{c,d}		Local softness ^e		Local electrophilicity ^f		Hardness potential ^g		Relative nucleophilicity ^h	Relative electrophilicity ⁱ	Dual descriptor ^j
		$f^+(k)$	$f^-(k)$	$s^+(k)$	$s^-(k)$	$\omega^+(k)$	$\omega^-(k)$	$\Delta^+h(k)$	$\Delta^-h(k)$			
LH	C14	3.8121	-0.6397	0.6660	-0.1118	5.0243	-0.8432	4.3609	4.3558	-0.1678	-5.9587	4.4518
	C21	10.1706	1.8352	1.7768	0.3206	13.4049	2.4187	5.0675	4.3991	0.1804	5.5421	8.3355
	N22	1.6713	0.8055	0.2920	0.1407	2.2028	1.0616	4.7313	4.2436	0.4819	2.0750	0.8659
	O23	-7.3172	0.6738	-1.2783	0.1177	-9.6441	0.8880	4.1063	3.8141	-0.0921	-10.8603	-7.9910
	N24	-3.9460	3.8978	-0.6894	0.6809	-5.2008	5.1373	4.4787	4.9343	-0.9878	-1.0124	-7.8437
	Cl25	0.7423	2.6510	0.1297	0.4631	0.9784	3.4940	3.3347	3.7358	3.5711	0.2800	-1.9086
	C26	5.0902	-0.5491	0.8893	-0.0959	6.7089	-0.7238	4.0005	4.3047	-0.1079	-9.2696	5.6393
	C27	-4.7800	-0.2231	-0.8351	-0.0390	-6.3000	-0.2941	3.9491	3.8906	0.0467	21.4220	-4.5569
	N30	-5.0886	3.7239	-0.8890	0.6506	-6.7067	4.9081	3.9777	4.6308	-0.7318	-1.3665	-8.8125
	<i>n</i> -Bu ₂ SnL ₂	Sn	1.1244	-0.0468	0.2425	-0.0101	1.6236	-0.0676	3.0167	2.5399	-0.0416	-24.0233
C70		0.3508	0.1382	0.0757	0.0298	0.5065	0.1996	2.9332	2.4212	0.3941	2.5374	0.2125
C73		0.3785	0.1592	0.0816	0.0343	0.5466	0.2299	2.7265	2.3230	0.4206	2.3778	0.2193
C14		0.4305	-0.1614	0.0929	-0.0348	0.6216	-0.2330	3.4913	2.5960	-0.3748	-2.6678	0.5919
C48		0.1491	-0.3581	0.0322	-0.0772	0.2153	-0.5171	2.2011	3.3304	-2.4015	-0.4164	0.5072
C21		3.0150	0.5382	0.6503	0.1161	4.3537	0.7772	4.0997	2.5988	0.1785	5.6016	2.4768
C55		0.5919	1.0125	0.1277	0.2184	0.8546	1.4621	2.3833	3.2699	1.7108	0.5845	-0.4207
N22		0.9559	0.2256	0.2062	0.0487	1.3804	0.3257	3.9331	2.6483	0.2360	4.2376	0.7304
N56		-0.3061	0.8656	-0.0660	0.1867	-0.4421	1.2499	2.3761	3.4020	-2.8276	-0.3537	-1.1717
O23		0.2893	-0.0063	0.0624	-0.0013	0.4177	-0.0090	3.2672	2.5919	-0.0216	-46.2174	0.2955
O57		0.0664	0.5486	0.0143	0.1183	0.0959	0.7922	2.6157	2.9501	8.2623	0.1210	-0.4822
N24		1.6041	1.4624	0.3460	0.3154	2.3164	2.1116	3.5395	2.8656	0.9116	1.0969	0.1418
N58		0.6144	2.5584	0.1325	0.5519	0.8872	3.6944	2.2604	3.7491	4.1639	0.2402	-1.9440
Cl25		1.2760	1.1584	0.2752	0.2499	1.8425	1.6727	2.7171	2.1754	0.9079	1.1015	0.1176
Cl59		0.6525	1.7429	0.1408	0.3759	0.9423	2.5168	1.8095	2.8124	2.6710	0.3744	-1.0904
C26		-0.2550	-0.0996	-0.0550	-0.0215	-0.3682	-0.1438	3.2789	2.7265	0.3906	2.5601	-0.1554
C60		-0.1132	-0.3020	-0.0244	-0.0652	-0.1635	-0.4362	2.2404	3.3908	2.6683	0.3748	0.1888
C27		-0.0876	-0.0699	-0.0189	-0.0151	-0.1265	-0.1010	3.2585	2.5605	0.7981	1.2529	-0.0177
C61	0.0329	-0.1445	0.0071	-0.0312	0.0475	-0.2086	2.3797	3.1331	-4.3884	-0.2279	0.1774	
N30	1.5268	1.3059	0.3293	0.2817	2.2048	1.8857	3.2678	2.8822	0.8553	1.1692	0.2210	
N64	0.4778	2.6461	0.1031	0.5708	0.6900	3.8209	2.2356	3.6357	5.5376	0.1806	-2.1682	

^aAll the values are in electron volt, except for relative electrophilicity and relative nucleophilicity; ^bAtom number as represented in Fig. 1; ^cFukui function [$f^\pm(k)$]: $f^+(k) = [p_{N+1}(k) - p_N(k)]$ and $f^-(k) = [p_N(k) - p_{N-1}(k)]$; ^d $p(k)$ is the electronic population on atom k in the neutral species (N), the cationic species ($N-1$) and the anionic species ($N+1$), where N is the number of electrons; ^eLocal softness [$s^\pm(k)$]: $s^+(k) = [p_{N+1}(k) - p_N(k)]S$ and $s^-(k) = [p_N(k) - p_{N-1}(k)]S$, where S is the global softness (= 0.1747 for LH and 0.2157 for *n*-Bu₂SnL₂); ^fLocal electrophilicity [$\omega^\pm(k)$]: $\omega^+(k) = [p_{N+1}(k) - p_N(k)]\omega$ and $\omega^-(k) = [p_N(k) - p_{N-1}(k)]\omega$, where ω is the electrophilicity index (= 1.318 for LH and 1.444 for *n*-Bu₂SnL₂); ^gHardness potential [$\Delta^\pm h(k)$]: $\Delta^+h(k) = h_{N+1}(k) - h_N(k)$ and $\Delta^-h(k) = h_N(k) - h_{N-1}(k)$, where $h(k) =$

$-V_{el}(k)$ (V_{el} being the electronic part of the molecular electrostatic potential); ^hRelative nucleophilicity defined as $\left(\frac{s^+(k)}{s^-(k)}\right)$; ⁱRelative

electrophilicity defined as $\left(\frac{s^-(k)}{s^+(k)}\right)$; ^jDual reactivity descriptor defined as: $f^2(k) = [f^+(k) - f^-(k)]$.

Table 2. Conceptual-DFT based local reactivity descriptors at the selected atoms in LH and *n*-Bu₂SnL₂ derivative, based on MPA scheme calculated at B3LYP/6-31G(d,p) and B3LYP/6-31G(d,p)/Def2-SVP(Sn) level of theory, respectively^{a,b,c}

System	Atom	Fukui function		Local softness		Local electrophilicity		Relative	Relative	Dual
		$f^+(k)$	$f^-(k)$	$s^+(k)$	$s^-(k)$	$\omega^+(k)$	$\omega^-(k)$	nucleo- philicity	electro- philicity	
LH	C14	0.3632	0.0762	0.0635	0.0133	0.4788	0.1005	0.2098	4.7658	0.2870
	C21	2.1409	0.9270	0.3740	0.1619	2.8217	1.2218	0.4330	2.3095	1.2139
	N22	0.6036	0.5063	0.1054	0.0885	0.7955	0.6673	0.8388	1.1921	0.0973
	O23	1.6238	1.3569	0.2837	0.2371	2.1402	1.7884	0.8356	1.1967	0.2669
	N24	1.7328	2.2538	0.3027	0.3937	2.2838	2.9705	1.3007	0.7688	-0.5210
	Cl25	2.4678	3.3699	0.4311	0.5887	3.2526	4.4415	1.3655	0.7323	-0.9020
	C26	0.1634	0.2002	0.0285	0.0350	0.2154	0.2639	1.2251	0.8162	-0.0368
	C27	1.6859	1.4087	0.2945	0.2461	2.2221	1.8567	0.8356	1.1968	0.2772
	N30	1.2961	2.1981	0.2264	0.3840	1.7083	2.8971	1.6959	0.5897	-0.9020
	<i>n</i> -Bu ₂ SnL ₂	Sn	0.6360	-0.0983	0.1372	-0.0212	0.9183	-0.1420	-0.1546	-6.4668
C70		0.1103	-0.0744	0.0238	-0.0161	0.1592	-0.1075	-0.6750	-1.4815	0.1847
C73		0.6518	0.6444	0.1406	0.1390	0.9412	0.9305	0.9886	1.0116	0.0075
C14		0.2107	0.0171	0.0454	0.0037	0.3042	0.0246	0.0810	12.3477	0.1936
C48		0.0458	0.0820	0.0099	0.0177	0.0662	0.1184	1.7892	0.5589	-0.0362
C21		1.6032	0.2674	0.3458	0.0577	2.3150	0.3861	0.1668	5.9953	1.3358
C55		0.2688	0.4667	0.0580	0.1007	0.3881	0.6740	1.7364	0.5759	-0.1979
N22		0.4754	0.1493	0.1026	0.0322	0.6865	0.2155	0.3139	3.1854	0.3262
N56		-0.2618	0.4913	-0.0565	0.1060	-0.3781	0.7094	-1.8762	-0.5330	-0.7531
O23		0.1144	-0.0256	0.0247	-0.0055	0.1652	-0.0369	-0.2234	-4.4760	0.1399
O57		0.2244	0.4188	0.0484	0.0903	0.3240	0.6048	1.8668	0.5357	-0.1945
N24		1.1332	0.8354	0.2444	0.1802	1.6364	1.2064	0.7372	1.3565	0.2978
N58		0.4834	1.4809	0.1043	0.3194	0.6980	2.1384	3.0636	0.3264	-0.9975
Cl25		1.8102	1.5122	0.3905	0.3262	2.6139	2.1836	0.8354	1.1971	0.2980
Cl59		0.9158	2.2536	0.1975	0.4861	1.3223	3.2542	2.4609	0.4063	-1.3379
C26		0.0699	0.1321	0.0151	0.0285	0.1009	0.1908	1.8898	0.5291	-0.0622
C60	0.1005	0.2603	0.0217	0.0561	0.1451	0.3759	2.5903	0.3861	-0.1598	
C27	1.1950	0.4507	0.2578	0.0972	1.7256	0.6509	0.3772	2.6513	0.7443	
C61	-0.2132	0.6480	-0.0460	0.1398	-0.3079	0.9357	-3.0388	-0.3291	-0.8612	
N30	0.9287	0.7896	0.2003	0.1703	1.3410	1.1402	0.8502	1.1762	0.1391	
N64	0.4573	1.5349	0.0986	0.3311	0.6603	2.2164	3.3565	0.2979	-1.0776	

^aAll the values are in electron volt, except for relative electrophilicity and relative nucleophilicity; ^bAtom number as represented in Fig. 1;

^cAll the local reactivity descriptors are as explained in Table 1.

greater the value of the condensed Fukui function, more reactive it will be²⁸. Moreover, for a nucleophilic attack due to an addition of an electron to the molecule, a positive value for Fukui function $f^+(\vec{r})$ at a particular atom emphasizes an increase of atomic population on that position, whereas a negative value means that the electron density is reduced. Similarly, for an electrophilic attack when an electron is removed from the molecule, a positive value for Fukui function $f^-(\vec{r})$ at a particular atom

emphasizes a decrease of atomic population on that position, whereas a negative value means that the electron density grows larger²⁸. Since, the local softness contains in addition to the Fukui function, information about the total molecular softness, therefore, it has been proposed by Chandra and Nguyen⁴², that the local softness values of individual atoms can be used to study relative site reactivity in a molecule i.e. the relative tendency of an atomic centre to behave as an electrophile or a nucleophile.

Fig. 2. Variation of Fukui index ($f^\pm(k)$) and local softness ($s^\pm(k)$) at the selected atoms in $n\text{-Bu}_2\text{SnL}_2$ based on NPA scheme calculated at B3LYP/6-31G(d,p)/Def2-SVP(Sn) level of theory.

Fig. 3. Variation of local electrophilicity index ($\omega^\pm(k)$) and hardness potential ($\Delta^\pm h(k)$) at the selected atoms in $n\text{-Bu}_2\text{SnL}_2$ based on NPA scheme calculated at B3LYP/6-31G(d,p)/Def2-SVP(Sn) level of theory.

As evident from the results (Table 1), in LH as well as in *n*-Bu₂SnL₂, the trends based on the values of $f^+(k)$, $s^+(k)$ and $\omega^+(k)$ with NPA scheme suggest that C21 is the most reactive site towards nucleophilic attack. Similar results are obtained with HPA scheme (*cf.* Table 3), however with MPA scheme C125 is found to be the most reactive site towards nucleophilic attack (*cf.* Table 2). Similarly, the trends based on the values of $f^-(k)$, $s^-(k)$ and $\omega^-(k)$ with NPA scheme suggest that, in LH N24_(diazepoxide ring) and in *n*-Bu₂SnL₂ N64 is the most

reactive site towards an electrophilic attack. However, with MPA and NPA schemes, in LH C125 and in *n*-Bu₂SnL₂ C159 is the most reactive site towards an electrophilic attack (*cf.* Tables 2 and 3).

The value of $f^+(k)$, $s^+(k)$ and $\omega^+(k)$ based on NPA scheme, at the central Sn atom in *n*-Bu₂SnL₂ is 1.1244 eV, 0.2425 eV and 1.6236 eV, respectively, whereas that of $f^-(k)$, $s^-(k)$ and $\omega^-(k)$ is -0.0468 eV, -0.0101 eV and -0.0676 eV, respectively. A positive and greater value of

Table 3. Conceptual-DFT based local reactivity descriptors at the selected atoms in LH and *n*-Bu₂SnL₂, based on HPA scheme calculated at B3LYP/6-31G(d,p) and B3LYP/6-31G(d,p)/Def2-SVP(Sn) level of theory, respectively^{a,b,c}

System	Atom	Fukui function		Local softness		Local electrophilicity		Relative	Relative	Dual
		$f^+(k)$	$f^-(k)$	$s^+(k)$	$s^-(k)$	$\omega^+(k)$	$\omega^-(k)$	nucleo-philicity	electro-philicity	
LH	C14	0.8141	0.3791	0.1422	0.0662	1.0730	0.4996	0.4656	2.1476	0.4350
	C21	2.0084	1.1123	0.3509	0.1943	2.6471	1.4660	0.5538	1.8057	0.8962
	N22	1.2085	0.7318	0.2111	0.1278	1.5929	0.9645	0.6055	1.6515	0.4767
	O23	1.4779	1.1565	0.2582	0.2020	1.9479	1.5242	0.7825	1.2779	0.3214
	N24	1.6869	2.3820	0.2947	0.4161	2.2233	3.1395	1.4121	0.7082	-0.6951
	C125	1.8103	2.6256	0.3163	0.4587	2.3859	3.4606	1.4504	0.6895	-0.8153
	C26	0.3669	0.5700	0.0641	0.0996	0.4836	0.7512	1.5535	0.6437	-0.2031
	C27	1.3207	1.0693	0.2307	0.1868	1.7407	1.4093	0.8097	1.2351	0.2514
	N30	1.3836	2.3294	0.2417	0.4069	1.8236	3.0702	1.6836	0.5940	-0.9458
	<i>n</i> -Bu ₂ SnL ₂	Sn	0.6865	0.0869	0.1481	0.0188	0.9913	0.1255	0.1266	7.8964
C70		0.3287	0.0568	0.0709	0.0123	0.4747	0.0821	0.1729	5.7827	0.2719
C73		0.5784	0.4219	0.1248	0.0910	0.8351	0.6092	0.7295	1.3709	0.1565
C14		0.5419	0.1871	0.1169	0.0404	0.7825	0.2702	0.3453	2.8960	0.3548
C48		0.2036	0.2908	0.0439	0.0627	0.2940	0.4199	1.4284	0.7001	-0.0872
C21		1.4764	0.3330	0.3185	0.0718	2.1319	0.4809	0.2256	4.4330	1.1433
C55		0.2788	0.5954	0.0601	0.1284	0.4025	0.8598	2.1361	0.4681	-0.3167
N22		0.9188	0.1903	0.1982	0.0411	1.3267	0.2748	0.2071	4.8276	0.7285
N56		-0.1080	0.6233	-0.0233	0.1344	-0.1560	0.9000	-5.7693	-0.1733	-0.7313
O23		0.3235	0.0103	0.0698	0.0022	0.4672	0.0149	0.0319	31.3720	0.3132
O57		0.1819	0.3956	0.0392	0.0853	0.2627	0.5712	2.1747	0.4598	-0.2137
N24		1.0499	0.8852	0.2265	0.1909	1.5161	1.2782	0.8431	1.1861	0.1647
N58		0.4342	1.5883	0.0937	0.3426	0.6270	2.2934	3.6580	0.2734	-1.1541
C125		1.3184	1.1583	0.2844	0.2498	1.9038	1.6726	0.8786	1.1382	0.1601
C159		0.6685	1.7462	0.1442	0.3767	0.9654	2.5215	2.6120	0.3829	-1.0777
C26		0.2489	0.2447	0.0537	0.0528	0.3595	0.3533	0.9829	1.0173	0.0042
C60		0.0639	0.4170	0.0138	0.0900	0.0923	0.6022	6.5273	0.1532	-0.3532
C27		0.9168	0.3310	0.1978	0.0714	1.3239	0.4779	0.3610	2.7700	0.5858
C61		-0.0693	0.4834	-0.0149	0.1043	-0.1000	0.6981	-6.9807	-0.1433	-0.5527
N30		0.9692	0.8058	0.2091	0.1738	1.3996	1.1636	0.8314	1.2029	0.1635
N64	0.3509	1.7004	0.0757	0.3668	0.5068	2.4554	4.8452	0.2064	-1.3495	

^aAll the values are in electron volt, except for relative electrophilicity and relative nucleophilicity; ^bAtom number as represented in Fig. 1;

^cAll the local reactivity descriptors are as explained in Table 1.

$f^+(k)$, $s^+(k)$ and $\omega^+(k)$ at the central Sn atom indicates that the central Sn atom is an electrophilic site and is more reactive towards a nucleophile, and that such an attack increases the atomic population at this centre. The value of $f^+(k)$, $s^+(k)$ and $\omega^+(k)$ (based on NPA scheme) at the coordinating oxygen atom O23 in *n*-Bu₂SnL₂ is 0.2893 eV, 0.0624 eV and 0.4177 eV, respectively, whereas that of $f^-(k)$, $s^-(k)$ and $\omega^-(k)$ is -0.0063 eV, -0.0013 eV and -0.009 eV, respectively. A slight negative value of $f^-(k)$ for O23 indicate that in case of an electrophilic attack the electron density grows slightly larger at this atom, though this centre within the complex have more reactivity towards a nucleophile owing to the positive and greater value for $f^+(k)$ in comparison to $f^-(k)$. However, the positive and greater value of $f^-(k)$, $s^-(k)$ and $\omega^-(k)$ (0.5486 eV, 0.1183 eV and 0.7922 eV, respectively) in comparison to $f^+(k)$, $s^+(k)$ and $\omega^+(k)$ (0.0664 eV, 0.0143 eV and 0.0959 eV, respectively) at the coordinating oxygen atom O57 in *n*-Bu₂SnL₂, indicates that it is a nucleophilic site and is more reactive towards an electrophile. Likewise, the positive and higher value of $f^+(k)$, $s^+(k)$ and $\omega^+(k)$ in comparison to $f^-(k)$, $s^-(k)$ and $\omega^-(k)$ for C70 and C73 also indicates that these two organic residues in *n*-Bu₂SnL₂ are electrophilic sites and more reactive towards a nucleophile (*cf.* Table 1). Similar trends are observed for these atomic sites in *n*-Bu₂SnL₂ based on MPA and HPA schemes (*cf.* Tables 2 and 3). Further, as evident from the results obtained from all the population schemes, the electron distribution in the two chlordiazepoxide (LH) units coordinated to *n*-Bu₂Sn(IV) moiety is unsymmetrical as various sites in the unit having O23 as a coordinating atom have greater and positive $f^+(k)$ favouring it for nucleophilic attack, whereas various sites in the unit having O57 as a coordinating atom have greater and positive $f^-(k)$ favouring it for an electrophilic attack. Furthermore, as evident from the results based on NPA charges (*cf.* Table 1) the atom with high electrophilicity (i.e. having high $f^+(k)$, $s^+(k)$ and $\omega^+(k)$ values) show low nucleophilicity (i.e. having low $f^-(k)$, $s^-(k)$ and $\omega^-(k)$ values). The results obtained are in accordance to the frontier molecular orbital analysis, which indicates that in *n*-Bu₂SnL₂ the HOMO is concentrated in the region containing the chlordiazepoxide unit with O57 as a coordinating atom and LUMO is concentrated around the central Sn atom and the chlordiazepoxide unit with

O23 as a coordinating atom. These results outline the general behaviour of the central Sn atom in the organotin(IV) complexes in accordance to the previously reported experimental observations, that R₂Sn(IV)²⁺ is an active species in the biological medium^{1,2,43}.

The two variants of the hardness potential viz. the electrophilic hardness potential ($\Delta^+h(k)$) and nucleophilic hardness potential ($\Delta^-h(k)$) have also been calculated at all the atoms of LH and *n*-Bu₂SnL₂, and the values for these two descriptors at the selected atoms are presented in Table 1. The values for these two descriptors at the selected atoms of *n*-Bu₂SnL₂ are presented in Fig. 3. The two descriptors $\Delta^+h(k)$ and $\Delta^-h(k)$ measures the reactivity towards an approaching nucleophilic and electrophilic reagent, respectively. A nucleophilic attack on an atom increases the electron density on it, resulting in a higher absolute value of $V_{el}^{N+1}(k)$ thereby making $\Delta^+h(k)$ a positive quantity. Normally, the higher the value of $\Delta^+h(k)$ at an atom, higher should be the reactivity (i.e. electrophilicity) of that atom towards an approaching nucleophile³⁷. Similarly, in case of an electrophilic attack on an atom the electron density gets reduced over it, resulting in a positive value of $\Delta^-h(k)$ as the absolute value of $V_{el}(k)$ of the atom decreases. Also, higher the positive value of $\Delta^-h(k)$ for an atom, higher should be the reactivity (i.e. nucleophilicity) of that atom towards an approaching electrophile. As evident from the results (*cf.* Table 1 and Fig. 3), in LH as well as in *n*-Bu₂SnL₂, the trends based on the values of $\Delta^+h(k)$ suggest that C21 is the most reactive site towards an approaching nucleophilic reagent. Similarly, the trends based on the values of $\Delta^-h(k)$ suggest that, in chlordiazepoxide N30 (*cf.* Table 1) and in *n*-Bu₂SnL₂ N58 (*cf.* Fig. 3) is the most reactive site towards an approaching electrophilic reagent. Further, the value of $\Delta^+h(k)$ and $\Delta^-h(k)$ at the central Sn atom in *n*-Bu₂SnL₂ is 3.0167 eV and 2.5399 eV, respectively, and at the coordinating oxygen atom O23 is 3.2672 eV and 2.5919 eV, respectively. The higher value of electrophilic hardness potential ($\Delta^+h(k)$) at the central Sn atom and O23 further indicates that these sites are more reactive towards a nucleophilic reagent. However, the value of $\Delta^+h(k)$ and $\Delta^-h(k)$ at the coordinating oxygen atom O57 is 2.6157 eV and 2.9505 eV, respectively. The higher value of nucleophilic hardness potential ($\Delta^-h(k)$) at O57 further indicates that this site is more reactive towards an electrophilic

reagent. Similarly, the carbon atoms in the $n\text{-Bu}_2\text{Sn(IV)}$ moiety bonded to the central Sn atom viz. C70 and C73 have higher value of electrophilic hardness potential ($\Delta^+h(k)$) further indicates the greater reactivity of these sites towards a nucleophilic reagent.

The variation of relative electrophilicity, relative nucleophilicity and dual reactivity descriptor at the selected atoms of $n\text{-Bu}_2\text{SnL}_2$ based on MPA, NPA and HPA charges is presented in Figs. 4(a), 4(b) and 4(c), respectively. Since, the MPA and NPA schemes gave negative Fukui index values for some of the atomic sites, therefore a comparative analysis of relative electrophilicity and relative nucleophilicity is presented based on HPA scheme. The relative electrophilicity helps to locate the preferable site (or atom) in a molecule for a nucleophilic attack on it and it is the electrophilicity of any site as compared to its own nucleophilicity, whereas the relative nucleophilicity helps to locate the preferable site (or atom) in a molecule for an electrophilic attack on it and it is the nucleophilicity of any site as compared to its own electrophilicity³⁴. As evident from the results (cf. Figs. 4(a) and 4(b)) O23 has maximum relative electrophilicity (31.3720 eV) based on HPA scheme, whereas O57 has maximum relative nucleophilicity (8.2623 eV) based on NPA scheme. Further based on HPA scheme (cf. Table 3 and Fig. 4(a)), in $n\text{-Bu}_2\text{SnL}_2$ apart from O23, the central Sn (7.8964 eV), C70 (5.7827 eV) and C73 (1.3709 eV) are also potential electrophilic sites, and thus, are the highly preferred sites for a nucleophilic attack, owing to a higher value of relative electrophilicity as compared to relative nucleophilicity. Apart from these sites, C14, C21, C26, N22 and N30 are also preferred sites for a nucleophilic attack. These results further indicate that, the charge density shifts away from the chlordiazepoxide unit with O23 as a coordinating atom. Furthermore, based on HPA scheme (cf. Fig. 4(b)), apart from O57 (2.1747 eV), N58 (3.6580 eV), N64 (4.8452 eV) and C60 (6.5273 eV) are also potential nucleophilic sites, and thus, are the highly preferred sites for an electrophilic attack, owing to higher value of relative nucleophilicity as compared to relative electrophilicity. Apart from these sites, C48, C55, C61 and N56 are also preferred sites for an electrophilic attack. These results further indicate that, greater charge density is concentrated over the chlordiazepoxide unit with O57 as a coordinating atom. Similar trends are observed

based on MPA and NPA schemes (cf. Tables 2 and 1).

The dual reactivity descriptor $f^2(k)$, a selectivity index is able to characterize both the nucleophilic and electrophilic behaviours. As evident from the results (cf. Tables 1, 2 and 3), in chlordiazepoxide (LH) among the selected atoms C21 has the most positive $f^2(k)$ value based on all the three population schemes (NPA : 8.3355 eV, MPA : 1.2139 eV and HPA : 0.8962 eV) and N30 has the most negative $f^2(k)$ value based on all the three population schemes (NPA : -8.8125 eV, MPA : -0.9020, and HPA : -0.9458 eV). Further, in $n\text{-Bu}_2\text{SnL}_2$ among the selected atoms C21 has the most positive $f^2(k)$ value based on all the three population Schemes (NPA : 2.4768 eV, MPA : 1.3358 eV and HPA : 1.1433 eV) (cf. Fig. 4(c)), indicating it to be most susceptible for a nucleophilic attack, whereas, N64 has the most negative $f^2(k)$ value based on NPA : -2.1682 eV and HPA : -1.3495 eV (cf. Fig. 4(c)), and C159 has the most negative $f^2(k)$ based on MPA : -1.3379 eV (cf. Fig. 4(c)) indicating these sites to be most susceptible for an electrophilic attack. Furthermore, the value of $f^2(k)$ based on NPA, MPA and HPA schemes at the central Sn atom is 1.1712 eV, 0.7343 eV and 0.5996 eV, respectively, and at the coordinating O23 in one of the chlordiazepoxide unit is 0.2955 eV, 0.1399 eV and 0.3132 eV, respectively. The value of $f^2(k)$ based on NPA scheme at the carbon atoms of the $n\text{-Bu}_2\text{Sn(IV)}$ moiety viz., C70 and C73 is 0.2125 eV and 0.2193 eV, respectively. However, the value of $f^2(k)$ based on NPA, MPA and HPA scheme at the coordinating O57 in the second chlordiazepoxide unit is -0.4822 eV, -0.1945 eV and -0.2137 eV, respectively. The positive value of $f^2(k)$ indicate that the central Sn atom, the two carbon atoms in the $n\text{-Bu}_2\text{Sn(IV)}$ moiety and the coordinating oxygen atom O23 are favoured for the nucleophilic attack, whereas negative value of indicate that the other coordinating oxygen atom O57 is favoured for an electrophilic attack.

An analysis of the results obtained from conceptual-DFT based local reactivity descriptors suggests that in $n\text{-Bu}_2\text{SnL}_2$ an external perturbation of electron distribution leads to redistribution of electron density in the complex in such a way that various atomic sites are either susceptible to an electrophilic or nucleophilic attack owing to respectively, an excess or deficient charge density at the respective atom. Further, the central Sn atom and the coordinating oxygen atom (O23) are susceptible to nu-

Fig. 4. Variation of (a) relative electrophilicity, (b) relative nucleophilicity, and (c) dual reactivity descriptor at the selected atoms of *n*-Bu₂SnL₂ derived from MPA, NPA and HPA schemes calculated at B3LYP/6-31G(d,p)/Def2-SVP(Sn) level of theory.

cleophilic attack, whereas the other coordinating oxygen atom (O57) is susceptible to an electrophilic attack. These results are in accordance to the frontier orbital analysis which reveals the concentration of HOMO in the chloridiazepoxide unit having O57 as the coordinating atom, whereas the LUMO is concentrated in the second unit having O23 as the coordinating atom.

Computational details

All the quantum chemical calculations have been performed using the Gaussian 09 program package⁴⁴. The molecular geometries of chloridiazepoxide (LH) and *n*-Bu₂SnL₂ were fully optimized in the gas phase at the DFT level using the B3LYP functional which is a combination of Becke's three parameter (B3) gradient corrected hybrid exchange functional⁴⁵, with the dynamical correlation functional of Lee, Yang and Parr (LYP)⁴⁶. All the atoms except Sn were described by 6-31G(d,p) basis set, which contains a reasonable number of basis set functions that are able to reproduce the experimental observations. The Sn atom in *n*-Bu₂SnL₂ was described by Ahlrich's basis set in its Def2-SVP version developed by Weigend⁴⁷, in which the inner core shells of Sn (1s²2s²2p⁶3s²3p⁶3d¹⁰) were described using the effective core potential of the Stuttgart group (ECP28MDF)⁴⁸, and outer shells were described by (10s7p6d)/[4s4p2d]. All the parameters of the basis sets and core potentials for Def2-SVP basis set were taken from the EMSL basis set exchange^{49,50}. The geometry optimization was carried out through an algorithm of iterative steps to locate true global minima on the potential energy surface (PES) with default parameters for convergence is met. The absence of an imaginary frequency in a harmonic frequency calculation carried out at the same level of theory indicates that the calculated geometry is a true global minimum on the PES. The optimized geometrical parameters and the atomic charges at all the atoms in the studied systems were calculated using Mulliken Population Analysis (MPA), Hirshfeld Population Analysis (HPA), and Natural Population Analysis (NPA) at the same level of theory. The energies of frontier molecular orbitals and studied conceptual-DFT based local reactivity descriptors based on MPA, HPA and NPA have been calculated using finite difference approximation^{27,51}. The visualization of all results have been performed using Gauss View 5.0⁵².

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